

INVESTIGATION AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF A SMALL SCALE SAVONIUS WATER CURRENT TURBINE IN PERSPECTIVE OF BANGLADESH

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Abstract- One of the finest renewable sources is hydropower from the river. Compared to wind or solar energy, hydropower is more predictable. Bangladesh has been blessed with many rivers with velocity of water flow. The savonius rotor is one of the finest forms of turbine for generating electricity utilizing the kinetic energy of natural water resources. There are many ongoing researches of using savonius water turbine to use it as a current turbine. In this study, the performance of a savonius water current turbine has been analyzed in respect to Bangladesh. To Analyze the performance, the Padma, the Ganga, the Brahmaputra, the Meghna and the Karnaphuli's water velocity has been taken into account. A Computer Aided Design (CAD) model of two blades of savonius water turbine was designed in SOLIDWORKS and analyzed with Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) in ANSYS simulation software. The performance has been analyzed with the comparison of flow rate, torque generated, Tip Speed Ratio (TSR), velocity and RPM. The velocity has been collected for the Padma, the Ganga, the Brahmaputra, the Meghna and the Karnaphuli as 4.86 ms^{-1} , 4.50 ms^{-1} , 3.5 ms^{-1} , 1.5 ms^{-1} and 0.44 ms^{-1} respectively.

Keywords: Computational Fluid Dynamics, Hydropower, Savonius Water Turbine.

1. INTRODUCTION

For the advancement of a nation, energy is the most essential industry. The needs for energy resources in emerging nations are presently growing quickly with economic expansion and industrialization. In recognition of the growing energy issue and global warming, several governments worldwide are beginning to spend a great deal of money and time on clean and renewable power [1].

The wind has a huge quantity of free energy accessible for conversion of energy. It is not a new notion that the use of wind machines to utilize electricity in water may be as long ago as the Chinese did in 2000 B.C. These early devices are employed for irrigation pumping water and then evolved for grain milling as windmills. Intense study and development into the utilization of water energy in electricity generation have only truly taken place in the recent century.

The savonius type vertical axis wind rotor was first invented by S. J. Savonius in 1929. The concept was based on the Flettner rotor idea. The rotor was made out of the Flettner cylinder being cut from top to bottom, and the two half-cylinder surfaces were then moved lateral along a cutting plane such that the cross-section looked like "S." It may be put directly in a water stream to create

mechanical energy from a moving fluid's kinetic energy. The concept is that a drag difference between the concentric and the convex, inducing a rotation, is generated. In comparison with other vertical axis turbines, such as the Darrieus rotor, the efficacy of the Savonius rotor is often low. The decreased efficiency is attributable to the fluid flow through the rotor blades producing positive and negative torques on both the leading and the trailing rotor blades. The usage of materials and production costs is reduced by Savonius rotors as lower size. Gorlov turbine, commonly known as "cross flow helical turbine," is patented by A. M. Gorlov [2]. It resembles Darrieus' turbine. Gorlov reported that the highest efficiency of the Gorlov turbine is around 35%, which is comparable to that of a Savonius water turbine. Mabrouk et al. [3] investigated that a new deflector system design can increase the efficiency of a three bladed helical savonius hydrokinetic turbine. Mohamed et al. [4] investigated that savonius rotor is a promising drag converter for low-speed fluid energy, but suffers from a low power output and efficiency. By enhancing its design, it can be led to higher values of power coefficient, thus obtaining better self-starting ability. Thochi et al. [5] evaluated the performance of several cluster configurations in an open water channel by modifying the gap distance and phase shift between the

turbines in order to identify their optimum values for an efficient cluster design in a two bladed savonius water turbine. Savonius rotor applications often include air pushing water, powered by an electric generator [6].

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The ANSYS WORKBENCH 2020 R2 and DS SOLIDWORKS 2018 operating systems have been used to originate the two bladed savonius type water turbine.

2.1 Specifications of turbine

Swept Area is the area of the encircle created by turbine blades as the blades sweep through the water [7]. The swept area can be expressed by Eq. (1). Where A is the swept area in meter², D is the diameter in millimeter and H is the height of turbine blade in millimeter.

$$A = D \times H \quad (1)$$

To determine the angular speed of blade, Eq. (2) is illustrated. Where n is number of rotation and ω is the angular velocity of blade.

$$\omega = \frac{2\pi n}{60} \quad (2)$$

To determine the flow rate of water, we use Eq. (3). Where A is the swept area and V is the water velocity.

$$q = A \times V \quad (3)$$

Water power [8] is calculated by using Eq. (4). Where C_p is co-efficient of turbine power, ρ is the density of water, A is swept area and V is water velocity.

$$P = \frac{1}{2} C_p \rho A V^2 \quad (4)$$

We can perceive the torque of turbine using Eq. (5). Where P is output power of turbine, n is number of rotations.

$$\tau = \frac{P}{n} \times \frac{30}{\pi} \quad (5)$$

Tip speed ratio (TSR) [9] is obtained by Eq. (6). Where ω is angular velocity, R is blade radius and V is velocity of water.

$$TSR = \frac{\omega R}{V} \quad (6)$$

The efficiency of turbine is calculated by using Eq. (7). Where P is power of turbine, m is mass of water, q is flow rate of water, g is gravitational acceleration and h is test height.

$$\eta = \frac{P}{mqgh} \quad (7)$$

3. EXPERIMENTAL DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1 refers different parameters for measuring the efficiency of the turbine. The velocity of water in the river's changes in dry season and rainy season. There may be variation in water velocity according to test height.

In this investigation, the mean velocity [10] has been taken.

Table 1: Data analysis for different rivers

River Name	Velocity (m/s)	Flow rate (m ³ /s)	TSR	Torque (N-m)	Power (watt)	Efficiency (%)
Padma	4.86	0.972	0.3232	255.262	4009.66	14.421
Ganga	4.50	0.90	0.3491	202.635	3182.996	13.352
Brahmaputra	3.50	0.70	0.4488	95.341	1497.624	10.385
Meghna	1.50	0.30	1.047	7.505	117.889	4.451
Karnaphuli	0.44	0.088	3.57	0.1894	2.975	1.305

The velocity of five rivers has been collected to measure the various parameters of turbine to be used in those rivers. Graphical analysis among TSR, velocity, flow rate, efficiency and torque has been shown in Fig. 1-4.

Fig. 1: Flowrate vs. TSR

Fig. 2: Velocity vs TSR

Fig. 3: Torque vs. Power

Fig. 4: Velocity vs. Efficiency

4. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

In this study, we analyzed the pressure and velocity of a savonius turbine. Figure 5 represents the

computational model of the simulation. To solve the problem, the governing equations were the three-dimensional Navier-Stokes equation and the continuity equation. We used the PISO model for coupling of the pressure and velocity. The inlet and outlet boundary condition were applied 15D and 15D far from the domain. The farfield was 10D away. The number of nodes in the grid was 120000. We run the simulation of a fixed Reynold's number of 1.3303×10^6 . The working fluid of the simulation was water (Density=1000 kg/m³). From the computational analysis in ANSYS, we have analyzed the pressure contours and velocity contours for mean velocity. The contours of pressure and velocity are illustrated from fig. 6 to fig. 9 respectively.

Fig. 5: 2D view of savonius turbine

Fig 6: Contours of absolute pressure

Fig 7: Contours of static pressure

Fig 8: Contours of total pressure

Fig 9: Contours of velocity magnitude

5. CONCLUSION

A model of savonius type water current turbine was designed and investigated. It was found that the hydraulic efficiency of the turbine increases with an increase in water velocity. 14.241% of efficiency was found as the maximum and 1.305% of efficiency was found as the minimum for the velocity of 4.86 ms^{-1} and 0.44 ms^{-1} respectively. The turbine gives higher mechanical power

output at higher velocity of water flow. It can be observed that this kind of turbine is cheaper to build and of high productivity considering not only the delivered power, but also the whole produced energy during a given period of time.

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8. NOMENCLATURE

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
A	Area of turbine blade	(m ²)
D	Diameter	(m)
H	Height of turbine blade	(m)
ω	Angular velocity	(rad.s ⁻¹)
Π	Pi	Dimensi onless
n	Number of rotations	Dimensi onless
q	Flow rate	(m ³ .s ⁻¹)
V	Velocity of water	(m.s ⁻¹)
P	Power output	(Watt)
C_p	Coefficient of power	Dimensi onless
ρ	Density of water	(Kg.m ⁻³)
τ	Torque	(N.m)
TSR	Tip speed ratio	Dimensi onless
R	Radius of turbine blade	(m)
η	Efficiency	Dimensi onless
m	Mass of water	(Kg)
g	Gravitational acceleration	(m.s ⁻²)
h	Test height	(m)